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Agricultural Biodiversity and its Contribution to Food Security: A Case Study in Tharu Community, Chitwan, Nepal

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to study the contribution of household agricultural diversity on food security in ethnic Tharu community of Terai, Nepal. Household (HH) surveys including field observations, key informant interviews and focus group discussions were conducted in four Village Development Committees (VDCs) (Khairahani, Meghauri, Gardi and Baghauda) to study agricultural biodiversity and its contribution to food security at HH levels. Out of 160 HHs, 40 HHs from each VDCs were surveyed by random sampling method. Structured and semi-structured questionnaires were used to conduct HH survey. The percentages of HHs involved in the study were 84% (Khairahani), 85% (Meghauri), 81% (Gardi) and 84% (Baghauda). Agriculture was the main occupation and 85% (Khairahani), 75.5% (Meghauri), 80% (Gardi) and 82% (Baghauda) had kitchen garden in their HHs. The number of diverse crops (crop biodiversity) per year in Tharu communities on-farm were the highest in Khairahani (54) followed by Baghauda (52), Gardi (50) and Meghauri (47). Positive linear correlation was observed between the number of months fulfilled by own production and the agricultural biodiversity was documented on farm and in the kitchen garden. The percentages of HHs that could feed for 12 months were 43% (Khairahani), 28% (Meghauri), 35% (Gardi) and 38% (Baghauda). Likewise, the percentage of HHs that could feed for >12 months were 50% (Khairahani), 45% (Meghauri) and 53% each in Gardi and Baghauda. The highest (70%) of the HHs consumed food thrice a day in Khairahani with the highest percentage of satisfaction (90%). The percentage of hunger satisfaction then decreased in the order; Baghauda (86%), Gardi (80%) and Meghauri (73%). More than 80% of the HHs in Khairahani, Gardi and Baghauda and more than 70% of HHs in Meghauri had food sufficiency. Hence, all the Tharu communities in the study areas were food secured. The

HHs that were familiar to food security in Khairahani, Meghauri, Gardi and Baghauda were 58%, 33%, 44% and 53% respectively.

Keywords

Agricultural biodiversity, Households, Food security, Tharu community

Introduction

Nepal is predominantly an agricultural country where 65.7% of the total population is engaged in agriculture (MoAC, 2009) sharing about 32.61% of Gross Domestic Production (GDP) (MoAD, 2014). Of the total land area of Nepal, about 21% (3.2 million hectares) is used for cultivation with principal crops viz. rice (45%), maize (20%), wheat (18%), millet (5%) and potatoes (3%), followed by sugarcane, jute, cotton, tea, barley, legumes, vegetables and fruits (Gautam et al 2008). However, Nepal is facing food insecurity especially after mid 1990's (IFPRI, 2009) due to poor agricultural growth, declined national agricultural priority, global climate change, global food crisis and political instability (Bista et al 2013). During this time, Nepal had national food deficit of 14.3% which varied by region with 79% in mountains, 36% in hills and the Terai region being the only area to produce a surplus of 7% (Gill et al 2003).

There are more than one hundred ethnic and caste groups in Nepal (CBS, 2003) each of them with their own type of food traditions. Tharu being the largest and the oldest ethnic group indigenous to the Terai region, the total population percentage in Nepal is 6.75% (CBS, 2001) and in Chitwan district, it is 12.74%. Before 1950, the total population of Chitwan (25,000) was mostly Tharu as the area was Malaria prone and they were the only inhabitants in the area. The entire lowland area of the Chitwan district was inhabited by the indigenous Tharu people, partially due to their resistance to malaria (Gurung, 1983; Gee, 1959). Fishing and collection of snails were essential parts of the Tharu diet fulfilling their protein needs. Gradually, cattle grazing and agriculture were primary activities of the community; with a heavy reliance on the forest resources. They collected minor forest products, food, household tools, and medicinal products. All these activities, important for the Tharu livelihood, were restricted after the establishment of the Chitwan National Park. Tharu were practicing shifting cultivation prior to the Nepal government's land registration and reform policy in early 1960's (Muller-Böker, 1993).

Agricultural biodiversity is the variety and variability of animals, plants & micro-organisms supporting food production and food security (FAO, 1999). Fuentes (2011) reported that biodiversity does not only mean about global species richness, but also includes diversity within species and between ecosystems and landscapes. On-farm agricultural biodiversity encompasses variation in agricultural produce in farmers' fields. Conservation of these produce focuses on conserving the cultivated plant species in farmers' fields (Jarvis et al 2000a) and continuous social and biological process of crop evolution on-farm (Brush, 1995). Agricultural diversity contributes to the secured livelihood through food security and also fulfills the social, cultural and religious needs of farmers. So, the single crop production as staple crop is less food secure (Wahlqvist, 2003). The diversity in crop production contributes to people livelihood directly through food production and indirectly through supporting and protecting human activities (Cromwell, 1999). Hence, on farm agricultural

biodiversity plays significant role in areas where alternative means of livelihood are little (Cooper et al 2001). In Nepal, crop diversity studies are limited to few crops like rice (Bajracharya et al 2003a), taro (Bajracharya et al 2003b; Rijal et al 2003a), finger millet (Tiwari et al 2003) and buckwheat (Bajracharya et al 2003c). However, production of cereals increased by only 5% whereas consumption requirement increased by more than 20% over the past eight years in Nepal (WFP, 2009).

Agricultural biodiversity contributes to food security via increasing food production and nutrition. FAO (2003) states the condition to be food secured when all people at all times have access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food to maintain a healthy and active life. Home gardens are important source of food, fodder, medicines, spices including that they contribute to on farm conservation of unique genetic resources for food and agriculture (Subedi et al 2004). In this research, contribution of agricultural biodiversity on food security in Tharu communities of Chitwan district was studied. Four Village Development Committees (VDCs) of Chitwan district viz. Khairahani, Megghauli, Gardi and Baghauda were selected where the presence of indigenous Tharu communities was prominent. General objective of this study is to assess the agricultural biodiversity at household level of Tharu communities and its linkage with food security. The study was done to assess degree of food security status, to correlate agricultural biodiversity to food security and to learn Tharu farmers' perception towards food security.

Materials and methods

This study used HHs survey, key informant interviews (KII), focus group discussions (FGDs) and field observations to generate qualitative and quantitative information about agricultural biodiversity and its contribution to food security. Primary information was acquired using FGDs with farmers and face-to-face interview. Out of total 160 HHs of four VDCs (Figure 1), 40 HHs from each VDCs were surveyed by random sampling method. FGD was organized for qualitative information based on their perceptions on agricultural biodiversity, hunger, poverty, balanced diet and food security. Progressive farmers and women groups were chosen for the group discussions. Key informants like Mukhiya of the VDC and learned people from the Tharu communities of each VDCs were asked about the agricultural practices they were following. Field observations were also done to collect primary information directly from the fields and kitchen garden. Crop diversity was calculated merely by counting the numbers of crops Tharu grew on farm. Research publications, journals, proceedings of various I/NGO, organizations (District Agriculture Development Office (DADO), Chitwan), Megghauli, Khairahani, Gardi and Baghauda VDCs were used so as to supplement and support the primary data. The data were analyzed by both descriptive and statistical tools, Statistical Packages for Social Science (SPSS) 16. The relationship and correlation between agricultural biodiversity and food security was studied by correlation analysis.

Figure 1: Map showing study areas

Results and discussion

Agriculture was the mainstay among the people in Khairahani, Meghauri, Gardi and Bagauda. From the study, 84% (Khairahani), 85% (Meghauri), 81% (Gardi) and 80% (Bagauda) were involved in agriculture. And, other people involved in small scale industries like shops, homestays, rod industry, etc. including agriculture.

Agricultural diversity in Tharu communities

HHs in different VDCs grew varieties of crops throughout the year. These crops included cereals, legumes, vegetables, fruits, oilseeds, spices, etc. (Table 1). The varieties of cereals were rice, summer rice, maize, wheat and buckwheat. The leguminous crops were lentil, pea, red kidney bean, soyabean, black gram and pea (small) and the vegetables like pumpkins, cowpea, potato, cauliflower, cabbage, spinach, broccoli, tomato, radish, bottle gourd, sponge gourd, bitter gourd, okra, eggplant, snake gourd and fava beans were grown. The fruits included mango, banana, papaya, sugarcane, guava and jackfruit. Sesame, mustard and linseeds were grown as oil seed crops. They used large number of spices in their food and these included coriander, turmeric, onion, garlic, chillies, cumin, Indian bay leaves, lemons, lime, ginger and garlic. Thus, the number of diverse crops per year in Tharu communities on-farm were the highest in Khairahani (54) followed by Bagauda (52), Gardi (50) and Meghauri (47). The different types of crops grown on farm are mentioned in the table as follows (Table 1):

Table 1: Inventory of on farm crops in Tharu communities

VDC	Khairahani	Meghauri	Gardi	Bagauda
Cereals	Rice, summer rice, maize, wheat, Buckwheat			

Legumes/pulses	Lentil, pea, pea (small), red kidney bean, soyabean, black gram	Lentil, pea, pea (small), black gram	Lentil, pea, pea (small), red kidney bean, black gram	Lentil, pea, pea (small), black gram, soyabean
Vegetables	Pumpkins, cowpea, potato, cauliflower, cabbage, broccoli, tomato, radish, faba beans, bottle gourd, bitter gourd, sponge gourd, okra, eggplant, spinach, snake gourd	Pumpkins, cowpea, potato, cauliflower, cabbage, broccoli, tomato, radish, faba beans, bottle gourd, bitter gourd, sponge gourd, okra, eggplant, ash gourd, spinach	Pumpkins, cowpea, potato, cauliflower, cabbage, broccoli, tomato, radish, faba beans, bottle gourd, bitter gourd, sponge gourd, okra, eggplant, spinach	Pumpkins, cowpea, potato, cauliflower, cabbage, broccoli, tomato, radish, faba beans, bottle gourd, bitter gourd, sponge gourd, okra, eggplant, spinach
Fruits	Sugarcane, banana, papaya, guava, mango, jackfruit	Sugarcane, banana, papaya, guava, mango, jackfruit	Sugarcane, banana, papaya, guava, mango, jackfruit	Sugarcane, banana, papaya, guava, mango, jackfruit
Oilseeds	Sesame, mustard	Sesame, mustard	Sesame, mustard, linseed	Sesame, mustard
Spices	Coriander, turmeric, onion, garlic, chillies, cumin, Indian bay leaves, lemons, lime, ginger	Coriander, turmeric, onion, garlic, chillies, cumin, Indian bay leaves, lemons, lime, ginger	Coriander, turmeric, onion, garlic, chillies, cumin, Indian bay leaves, lemons, lime, ginger	Coriander, turmeric, onion, garlic, chillies, cumin, Indian bay leaves, lemons, lime, ginger

Kitchen garden

There were HHs which grew crops which included mainly vegetables in some seasons, the other HHs grew crops all the year round and some HHs had no kitchen garden. The percentages of kitchen garden in Khairahani, Megghauli, Gardi and Bagghauda were 85%, 75.5%, 80% and 82% respectively (Figure 2). Likewise, the remaining 15%, 24%, 20% and 18% respectively did not own kitchen garden in Khairahani, Megghauli, Gardi and Bagghauda VDCs. 58%, 56%, 50% and 38% of the HHs in Khairahani, Bagghauda, Gardi and Megghauli grew vegetables all the year round.

Figure 2: Kitchen garden in Tharu communities

Food sufficiency

From the HH survey, it was found that 3% of the people in Megghauli and Bagghauda fed the people for only less than 3 months (Figure 3). 10% and 3% of the people fed for 6 months in Megghauli and Bagghauda respectively. Likewise, 8%, 15%, 13%, and 5% of the people fulfilled their hunger in Khairahani, Megghauli, Gardi and Bagghauda respectively for 9 months. 43%, 28%, 35% and 38% of the people in Khairahani, Megghauli, Gardi and Bagghauda respectively produced crops sufficient to feed for 12 months. Finally, 50%, 45%, 53% and 53% of the people in Khairahani, Megghauli, Gardi and Bagghauda respectively produced crops sufficient to feed for more than 12 months.

Figure 3: VDC-wise food fulfillment percentage from field production

Household food consumption and hunger satisfaction

Generally, Tharus consumed rice thrice a day, once in the morning, once in the day time as lunch and once in the evening. 70% HH in Khairahani consumed food thrice a day and remaining 30% consumed twice a day. Here, unlike 10% of the HH, 90% of the HH had hunger satisfaction. Likewise, in respective Megghauli, Gardi and Bagghauda VDCs, 44%, 65% and 64% of the HH consumed their food thrice a day followed by 56% (Megghauli), 35% (Gardi) and 36% (Bagghauda) twice a day (Figure 4). In Megghauli, Gardi and Bagghauda VDCs, the hunger satisfaction percentages were 73%, 80% and 86% respectively.

Figure 4: Household food consumption per day and hunger satisfaction (%)

Correlation between agricultural biodiversity and food security

Positive linear correlation was observed between the number of months fulfilled and the agricultural biodiversity observed on farm and in the kitchen garden (Figure 5). The total months fulfilled and the crop diversity in Khairahani showed the highest and positive linear correlation. This meant that when there was more diversification in agricultural crops, the number of months fulfilled also increased. The coefficient of determination (R^2) value was 0.989; it meant that the contribution of diversified crops on the number of months to be hunger fulfilled was 98.90%. These values decreased in the order 0.977 (Baghauda), 0.936 (Gardi) and 0.614 (Meghauri). These indicated that the contributions of diversified crops on the number of months to be hunger fulfilled were 97.70% (Baghauda), 93.60% (Gardi) and 61.40% (Meghauri).

Figure 5: Relationship between number of months fulfilled in a year by the diversified agricultural crops in Khairahani, Meghauri, Gardi and Baghauda VDCs

Household knowledge on food security

In Khairahani, 58% of the HH knew about the food security and the remaining 42% were unknown. Likewise, 33% (Meghauri), 44% (Gardi) and 53% (Baghauda) were familiar to food security. And, 67%, 56% and 47% of the HH in Meghauri, Gardi and Baghauda respectively did not know about food security (Figure 6).

Figure 6: HH knowledge on food security

Conclusion

Varieties of crops like cereals, oil seeds, legumes, vegetables, fruits and spices were grown on farm depending on literacy rates, accessibility to roads and land holdings. Thus, the inventory of agricultural biodiversity in Tharu communities was reported. More than 80% of the HHs in Khairahani, Gardi and Baghauda and more than 70% of HHs in Meghauri had food sufficiency. Hence, all the Tharu communities in the study areas were food secured. Agricultural biodiversity and food security in Tharu communities was positively correlated. There was strong correlation in Khairahani and the strength decreased in order: Khairahani > Baghauda > Gardi > Meghauri. Majority of Tharu people were unknown about the perceptions on food security.

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